

STATUS OF EDUCATION IN PUNJAB

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ABSTRACT

Education is one of the critical inputs in economic development and crucial factor in the creation of a civil society. It develops the capability of citizens of a country through schooling for the purpose of diffusion of knowledge and various skills. Highly skilled and trained human beings are definitely more productive than illiterate and unskilled persons. They have the capacity to better organize their social and economic environment and resources. Therefore, having greater productivity, the education is not only a vehicle of upward social and economic mobility of individuals but of the society as a whole. In fact, education has enormous amount of private and social returns.

KEY WORDS: Education, Constitution, Government, Primary, Provisions, Status.

INTRODUCTION

The history of the development of education in India can be traced back from the ancient times. It is believed that there were three types of informal institutions which provide education to the few selected. Firstly, Gurukuls were made to keep the students away from the distraction of the material world, amidst natural surroundings. The students comprehend all the intricate problems of life through listening and meditation. Secondly, the Parishads used to provide knowledge for higher learning, gathered and queried their insatiable thirst for knowledge, through discussion and dialogue. Thirdly, The Sammelans were the rare occasions where the kings used to invite several scholars, rashes, philosophers, theologians and psychologists to national gatherings for discussion and debates on important issues.

EVOLUTION OF EDUCATION SYSTEM

The system of modern education in India began with the coming of Britishers in eighteenth century. Initially, the East India Company was reluctant to open any educational institution even at lower level. But, after its complete control over Bengal it needed local population for petty jobs which required formal education. Warren Hasting was the first representative of the British rule in India who set up Calcutta Madrass in 1781 for the study of Persian and Arabic. In 1791, Jonathan Duncan, a British resident, opened Sanskrit College at Banaras for the teaching of laws, literature and religion to the Hindus. But these attempts met with little success. The coming of Christian missionaries in India changed the education scenario as they opened many schools in urban and rural areas.

Under Charter Act of 1813, a sum of Rs. one lakh was kept for the revival and promotion of literature and the encouragement of the learned natives of India. Because the objective was to create a class of persons who could write and speak english to help the administrative work which later on became standardized system of education. After that the process of modern education began particularly when the British annexed Punjab in 1849. The Wood's Dispatch Act, 1854 known as the Magna Carta of English education in India touched all aspects of education. It proposed the setting up of vernacular primary schools in the villages at the lowest stage. The Department of Public Instruction under the charge of a Director was established to review the progress of education and to submit annual report to the government. It also recommended a system of grants-in-aid to encourage and foster private

enterprise in the field of education. Thereafter, W.W. Hunter Commission emphasized the role of state to provide special care for the extension and improvement of primary education. It recommended the recognition of aided schools as equal to government institutions in matters of status, privileges etc. Punjab University was founded in 1882 as the supreme literary, teaching and examining body in undivided Punjab. Meanwhile, the British government made efforts for the spread of education and recommended a system of grants-in-aid to engage and foster private enterprise in the field of education. The second half of the 19th century witnessed many changes in social-political set up in the country. The rise of communal consciousness and competition to grab new opportunities resulted into a major competition among the three communities i.e. Hindus, Muslims and Sikhs to open more and more educational institutions. Though, the basic objective of the missionaries was to preach Christianity, but it laid the foundation of modern private management schools. It was followed by the opening of schools and colleges by the local religious and social leaders. The founder of Arya Samaj, Swami Dayanand Saraswati laid great emphasis on education. The D.A.V. institutions spread over the length and breadth of the country and they are a standing roof of the educational achievements of the Samaj. Free India needs effective Constitution to provide Justice, Liberty, and Equality and of course, to provide free education to the students of India. Finally a new constitution for free India became effective from 26th January 1950.

CONSTITUTION ARTICLES

- Free and compulsory primary education in the country – Article 45 of the India Constitution explains that the State shall endeavor to provide within a period of ten years from the commencement of this Constitution for free and compulsory education for all children until they complete the age of fourteen years.
- Religious instruction – Article 28(1), Article 28(2), Article 28(3) and Article 30 of the Indian Constitution safeguard the Secular Education. India is a secular state and every religion has got the right to popularize and spread its religious ideals.
- Equality of Opportunity in Educational Institutions – Article 29 and 30 of the Indian constitution guarantee the minorities certain cultural and educational rights to establish and administer educational institutions of their choice, whether based on religion or language.
- Education of the socially and educationally backward classes of citizens – Article 15, 17 and 46 safeguard the educational interest of the weaker sections of the Indian community that is socially and educationally backward classes of citizens and scheduled castes and scheduled tribes.
- Language and educational safeguard – Article 29 (1) explains that any section of the citizens, residing in the territory of India or any part there having a distinct language, script or culture of its own shall have the right to construct the same.

The above mentioned articles and some others which are provided by the Indian Constitution to popularize the education among Indian citizens is able to fill the gap of educational disparities between rural and urban, between male and female, between rich and poor and provide maximum possibilities to get education with minimum expenditure.

WHAT HAS BEEN DONE BY GOVERNMENT

The immediate action taken by Government of India after independence was the formation of University Education Commission in 1948 under the chairmanship of Dr. S. Radha Krishnan which submitted its report in 1949. While the Radha Krishnan committee recommends

constitution and functions at the university level like the financial sources for University, Process of admission, courses, and lastly; the responsibility for the development of university level education. After Independence the government of India shared the responsibility of development in various sectors, including education within its states by adopting federal form of government and through three different lists, such as union list which includes items of interest to the nation, second one is state list which includes items of local interest and last on is concurrent list which includes concern both the centre and the state. With the establishment of planning commission in the same year when India was proclaimed a Republic, the task of drawing five-year plans covering all aspects of national development was included in education. The total investment in education sector was 153 cores in first five year plan (1950-51) which represented 7.8 percent of the total plan outlay. After establishment and implementation of University Commission's recommendation, India moved towards the development of entire education system.

To construct the fresh and more effective system in the field of education, the Kothari Commission was appointed in 1964-66 to advise the government on national pattern of education for development of education at all stages and in all aspects. The commission was led by Dr. D.S. Kothari as a chairman. According to the report submitted by Kothari Commission, the state and national level machinery will define, revise and evaluate national standards of education. It also suggested for the setting up of National Board of school education to channelize the school education in a proper way. While after careful consideration and nation-wide discussion on the Report of this commission, government realized the absence of policy particularly, in education. So, without any delay government of India declared the National Education Policy in 1968. An agricultural university was established at Ludhiana in 1956 and Punjab University was shifted to Chandigarh in 1959. Later on, two more universities i.e. Punjabi University Patiala and Kurukshetra University in Kurukshetra were opened in early 60s to give major boost to the higher education.

The Green Revolution, in the state in late sixties brought radical transformation in all fields including education. It has tended the process of opening of new educational institutions in urban and rural Punjab. The post-green revolution era opened new opportunities and increased demand of workforce in skilled, semi-skilled and unskilled fields. This process provided a major boost to the overall growth in the state as Punjab became number one state in India in economic terms. On the other hand, the state and central governments provided liberal financial assistance for opening new educational institutions in the state. It brought rapid expansion of education particularly in rural areas. The office of education department which was shifted from Lahore to Shimla in 1947, was brought back to Chandigarh in 1959. The education secretary used to be the Director of Public Instructions. Punjab University, Chandigarh, remained the examining body of both high schools and colleges in the state till Punjab School Education Board was created in 1969. After that, the school examination is being managed by Punjab School Education Board. Another, important development in this period was the opening of a new university in Amritsar in the name of first Guru of the Sikhs i.e. Guru Nanak Dev University on his five hundred birth century celebrations. It is to mention here that the year 1969, was dedicated to the spread of education as large number of colleges and schools were opened in rural and urban areas in the state.

ROLE OF EDUCATION

The contribution of education in economic growth and human capital formation is of critical importance and multidimensional. The character and pace of economic growth and development of a country is unnaturally determined by the quality of human resources apart

from other factors. The human resource being an active factor of production, accumulates knowledge, builds social, economic and political organization and carries forward the project of national development. Education is inherently a time and labour consuming process which generates long chain of expertise for the economy, society and polity. It affects whole range of activities both in the market and non-market spheres of production. It is being held that education generates both social returns as well as private returns. The relative magnitude of the various returns depends upon quality, type and stage of education. Role of education in developing societies is more pronounced and critical. Apart from economic benefits, the education imparts new ideas, values, and attitudes and is helpful in behavioral transformation by making individual more liberal and dynamic in out-look and action.

Impact of education on individual earning is very significant and is helpful in the reduction of poverty and unemployment. Women education is very much important in the society because of its direct impact on household set up, family pattern and size. The education of women affects their fertility behavior primarily by the mechanism of rising. The small family sizes are associated with educated and working mothers. Women education results in rising their marriage age and consequently, lowering the birth rate. Education, provided with relevant content and impacted in right environment can be very helpful in rural and agriculture development which various studies have established. Those agriculture revolutions emerged at those places where farmers are more educated and trained. Educated farmers are expected to be more receptive to the newer techniques, newer information, modern chemical nputs and adoption of better marking, storage and organization practices. The productivity and efficiency levels were higher in the unit of educated farmers. The diversification of rural economy is strongly contingent upon the education of the farmers, agricultural workers, rural women as well as that of rural artisans and other sections of society. The egalitarian character of rural education system is the pre-condition to attain smooth rural transformation. Economics of education is the newest range in the science of economics. The stagnation thesis has yielded place to a new wave of optimism based on investment in human capital. The fundamental problem is no longer considered to be the creation of wealth, but rather the creation of the capacity to create wealth. The capacity to create wealth comes through brain power as is developed through education where the older generation took education as akin to capital.

Education affects productivity in the following ways: (a) It adds to the stock of knowledge and spreads it in the economy. (b) It maintains skills by passing them on from generation to generation. (c) It maintains and carries forward the cultural heritage in the form of student's attitudes to life and work at the same time rationalizes. The old attitudes are in line with the demands of modern life. Education can keep the society in its traditional bounds or lift it out into modern age. Education, in general and the school education, in particular have its own importance in a vast and developing country like India where 70 percent of the population lives in rural area. Primary education works as a liner in raising financial and social status of an individual economic condition of a country that depends largely upon on educational standards of its student. Primary education is shaped according to the prevailing social and philosophical milieu and is regarded as foundation for the entire super centrist of children's moral; spiritual intellectual and physical development. Primary school will help to develop those basic skills, independence and initiative for successfully solving the problems. It strives for the discovery and full development of all the human and constructive talent of each individual. The other function of primary education pertains to the development of new behavior pattern and attitudes. Education enables the individual to cope with the new situations in the society. It instills the idea of progress. Primary education shoulders the

greatest responsibility in the national upliftment. The student's future depends warily upon what he has gained in the primary schools, is accordingly been mentioned in the UNESCO document (1972).

The primary level education can be seen as the most sensitive area of educational planning and development. Firstly, because pupils who enter at the age of five or six are, "Scheduled" to leave at 12 or 14, acquire at those impressionable ages throughout parents and habits that will affect throughout their lives. Secondly, because primary education bears the trend of today's education explosion. Thirdly because, many young students especially in rural areas, never receive any further school experience. Fourthly, because every egalitarian frame work mostly provide minimum learning skills to all (UNESCO, 1972).

ECONOMIC GROWTH AND EDUCATION

Role of education is most important in all sectors. Nowadays education is most important for economic growth. Education provides a foundation for development, the groundwork on which much of our economic and social well-being is built. It is the key to increase economic efficiency and social consistency. By increasing the value and efficiency of their labour, it helps to raise the poor from poverty. It increases the overall productivity and intellectual flexibility of the labour force. It helps to ensure that a country is competitive in world markets now, characterized by changing technologies and production methods. By increasing a child's integration with dissimilar social or ethnic groups early in life, education contributes significantly to nation building and interpersonal tolerance. Education plays a major role in the economic development of any country, may it be developed or developing. Many resources play a part in the growth of a country, one of which and perhaps the most important is human capital, which means the work force of the country. A good and productive work force, by making use of other resources can lead an economy to growth and prosperity. Education, in every sense, is one of the fundamental factors of development. No country can achieve sustainable economic development without substantial investment. Education enriches students' understanding of themselves and world. It improves the quality of their lives and leads to broad social benefits to individuals and society. Education raises students' productivity and creativity and promotes entrepreneurship and technological advances. In addition it plays a very crucial role in securing economic and social progress and improving income distribution.

CONCLUSION

There are many channels through which education affects economic growth, productivity and development in general. It enhances the ability of an individual to perform standard tasks and to learn to perform new tasks. It also enhances the ability of an individual to receive and process new information. It further improves the ability of individuals to communicate and therefore to coordinate activities with one another. Education enhances the ability of an individual to evaluate and adjust to changed circumstances and helps to reduce, subjective uncertainty and unnecessary ancient as well as fatalistic acceptance of the status quo and there by enhances the probability of adoption of new technologies or practices by an individual. Finally at higher levels, education also helps to bring about innovations in the production technology. Hence a country with a strong education system can be more developed in the future

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